

Deliverable D4.2 – Role description: Dissemination to businesses and the public

OPENing UP new methods, indicators and tools for peer review, impact measurement and dissemination of research results

Project acronym: OpenUP

Grant Agreement no. 710722

Deliverable/Milestone information	
Deliverable number and name	D4.2 – Role description: Dissemination to businesses and the public
Due date	2018-06-30
Delivery	2018-06-30
Work Package	WP4
Lead Partner for deliverable	AIT
Author	Michela Vignoli, Jan Rörden
Reviewers	Mappet Walker
Approved by	All partners
Dissemination level	Public
Version	1.0

Table 1. Document revision history

Issue Date	Version	Comments
2018-04-13	0.1	Outline
2018-05-24	0.2	Integrated input by WP4 team
2018-06-05	0.3	Final draft for internal review
2018-06-18	0.4	Review by M. Walker
2018-06-21	1.0	Final document addressing comments by reviewer
2018-06-28	1.0	Final version with minor additions

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OpenUP is a project partially funded by the European Union

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Summary

The changing open science landscape leads to new requirements imposed on researchers in terms of dissemination and outreach. Communicating research results to businesses, the public, and other target groups outside the fellow researcher community requires specific skills. To communicate research outcomes to these target groups, it is necessary to produce texts tailored for them, e.g. avoiding technical jargon, using alternative formats like video, GIF animations, comics, etc.

Traditionally research organisations rely on their marketing and communication departments/staff or specialist media for this task. However, with the increasing availability and importance of micro blogging, social media and other interactive Web 2.0 communication tools for communicating research outcomes to target audiences outside academia, pressure on researchers to apply more marketing oriented communication strategies and content increases. To meet the recent expectations by research funders, citizens and other stakeholders in terms of opening up research dissemination, it is necessary to rethink the established roles of researchers and science communicators. Communicating research to the general public is a very different task than communicating it to peers.

For the developing open science communication to be sustainable and efficient, we think that it is of utmost importance to support newly emerging niches facilitating researchers, open science communicators and PR departments to closely work together. We need to think out of the box and develop feasible solutions. In this deliverable we suggest creating a new role for open science communication and suggest a definition of this newly emerging role. It can be seen as an intermediary role lying in between the roles of researcher, science journalist, and PR/communication.

Reaching out to public target audiences requires specific skills for which researchers are traditionally not trained for. As we have made clear in this document, there is an **increasing need to fill the gap between scientific, “complex” dissemination to an expert public and a more popular, “simplified” communication to public target audiences**. Targeted and interactive Open Science Communication should be supported on policy and institutional level to increase active participation by researchers. In this context, additional **funding** of science communication activities, setting appropriate **incentives** and providing communication and soft-skills **training** for researchers are key factors.

We propose to **create new science communication roles and positions** to be staffed with people both **skilled in science communication and with science expert knowledge**. It is important to have, next to PR and marketing staff, trained experts with the necessary scientific background and skills, who are also trained in communicating to and interacting with audiences outside the research community by means of Web 2.0 technologies. Policy makers and strategic HR should see this as a chance to create new jobs for the growing number of qualified young researchers, who currently only have poor access to the job market in research and academia.

1. Introduction

Dissemination of research has changed considerably following the digitisation of science. Innovative ways to disseminate research information, e.g. via blogs, social media or video streaming platforms, are increasingly becoming an essential part of research dissemination. Among other, this development has been fuelled by the push towards public understanding of science and research since the 1980s, and a growing emphasis on engagement and participation of non-research audiences (Beaufort 2016).

During the first year of the OpenUP project we did a landscape scan of projects applying innovative dissemination methods and a survey asking researchers about their views on and experiences with innovative dissemination¹. In the resulting deliverable (D4.1) we presented theories and models of dissemination going beyond academia as part of innovative scholarly communication, and discussed factors affecting engagement of the general public and other non-academic actors with science and technology. The two most striking lessons learned are that dissemination in an open science context is increasingly done at earlier stages of the research lifecycle, and that it becomes more interactive.

The landscape scan and the survey revealed a wealth of approaches going beyond traditional academic publishing. While we can observe enthusiastic uptake with specific groups of researchers, the survey results also showed a gap in practice when it comes to innovative dissemination. Communicating to a wider audience seems to be more of a developing norm with early adopters than a widely exercised practice. Lack of knowledge about innovative dissemination channels and methods are important barriers for adoption, especially for young researchers. To meet the new requirements and expectations from funders and the society at large, further support for the stakeholders involved is needed.

To address this gap, we developed an innovative dissemination framework². It is designed to give stakeholders recommendations for innovative dissemination practices tailored to their requirements and their resources. To complement the guidelines and dissemination framework for EU funded research provided in D4.1 (Kraker et al. 2017), with this deliverable we provide additional guidance for research organisations and HR. This document summarises the guidelines and recommendations for researchers on how to reach out for two target audiences: businesses and the general public. In addition, it will help organisations in planning and adapting resource and personnel management to the emerging science communication needs for targeting stakeholders beyond the research community.

Reaching out to businesses and general public target audiences requires specific skills. Researchers are traditionally not trained for this kind of dissemination, but rather to communicating research results to their peers, which results in a competency gap. In this document we provide a skills profile for communicating research outcomes in an open science world. It can be used as resource for training and personnel planning in HR.

1.1. Issue overview

The changing open science landscape leads to new requirements imposed on researchers in terms of dissemination and outreach. Communicating research results to businesses, the public, and other target groups outside the fellow researcher community requires specific skills. To communicate research outcomes to these target groups, it is necessary to produce texts tailored for them, e.g. avoiding technical jargon, using alternative formats like video, GIF animations, comics, etc.

Traditionally research organisations rely on their marketing and communication departments/staff or specialist media for this task. However, with the increasing availability and importance of micro blogging, social media and other interactive Web 2.0 communication tools for communicating research outcomes to target audiences outside academia, pressure on researchers to apply more marketing oriented communication strategies and content increases. The OpenUP survey conducted last year showed that in terms of innovative dissemination there is a substantial gap. Only a minority of researchers targets non-academic audiences frequently and also dissemination channels specifically designed for doing so are used only by a small share of researchers on a regular basis. Just 12% of

¹ Kraker et al. 2017

² <https://www.openuphub.eu/disseminate>

respondents reported to having achieved an outstanding result using innovative dissemination channels³.

In practice, only limited support is provided to researchers for this kind of activity. This certainly is one of the reasons why innovative dissemination practices are picked up slowly by researchers. However, there is another important reason. Traditionally, science dissemination is divided between dissemination of research outcomes to peers, which is done by researchers (e.g. at conferences, in scientific publications); and popular, general public-targeted communication of research information, which is traditionally done by research journalists or communication departments. The impact of Web 2.0 communication channels is slowly but steadily blurring this division and requires rethinking of this distinct division of roles.

To meet the recent expectations by research funders, citizens and other stakeholders in terms of opening up research dissemination, it is necessary to rethink the established roles of researchers and science communicators. Communicating research to the general public is a very different task than communicating it to peers. As Jessica Eise⁴ puts it, “All forms of professional communication require the same broad, cross-cutting skill set. Yet each sub-discipline requires an orientation and focus on different pieces.” The interviewed science communication experts confirmed that doing communication well is a big job, and it does not necessarily lead to success. You can do it right and still fail to reach a lot of impact. It is no coincidence that research and communication are traditionally two different jobs. It is unrealistic to put the additional work of open science communication on top of the other tasks already done by researchers. However, for an immediate and interactive open science communication to work it is important to have, next to PR and marketing staff, trained experts with the necessary scientific background and skills, who are also trained in communicating to and interacting with audiences outside the research community using the web and social media. We cannot deny the increasing importance of communicating and interacting with the public to improve perception and awareness of science and to educate and inform the general public (Eagleman 2013, Libutti & Valente 2006, Callon 1999). Mass media outlets have lost their former dominant position compared to the increasing importance of social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter and YouTube to reach public audiences (Fingerle 2017). That is why it is necessary to re-think science communication in terms of possibilities offered by Web 2.0 technologies.

For the developing open science communication to be sustainable and efficient, we think that it is of utmost importance to support newly emerging niches facilitating researchers, open science communicators and PR departments to closely work together. We need to think out of the box and develop feasible solutions. In this deliverable we suggest creating a new role for open science communication and suggest a definition of this newly emerging role. It can be seen as an intermediary role lying in between the roles of researcher, science journalist, and PR/communication.

1.2. Approach and methodology

As a first step towards defining communication standards for reaching general public and business target audiences using open science communication forms/formats, we interviewed 7 individual science communication experts (4 male, 3 female) to elicit the requirements of the targeted audiences⁵. The interviews took between 20-60 minutes. We asked the experts about needs and expectations of businesses and the general public in terms of dissemination of research results, and their experiences on how the information should be structured and communicated to be useful and appealing for them. Also, we asked them to share some success stories and recommendations for researchers with us. A summary of requirements and expectations by business and general public stakeholders is given below (2.1 Stakeholder analysis).

Based on this, we proposed communication guidelines and recommendations for reaching businesses and the public. Good practices for defining targeted key messages and choosing the right format for communicating to the target audiences are summarised in chapter 2.2. An overview table of the draft

³ Kraker et al. 2017, 23 ff.

⁴ Eise 2016

⁵ Vignoli 2017, 19 ff.

recommendations and guidelines is included in Appendix I. The guidelines, which are mainly targeting researchers and science communicators, have been published on the OpenUP Hub⁶.

To define the newly emerging role of open science communicator we did a desk research of existing role and job descriptions as well as papers and studies about science communication beyond academia (2.3 Analysis of existing role descriptions matching required skills and task description). To the best of our knowledge, we strived to consider current developments, expectations and needs by all key stakeholders involved (i.e. researchers, business and general public target audiences, research funders, and research organisations). As a result, we propose a role definition of open science communication, which is included in chapter 3 (Defining the role of Open Science Communication Expert).

1.3. Definitions

According to the EC's definition⁷, **communication** in EU projects has the purpose to

- Show the added value that projects provide to scientific excellence, Europe's competitiveness, and for solving societal challenges.
- Show the relevance of the project's results for our everyday lives (e.g. creating jobs, novel technologies, making our lives more comfortable).
- Make better use of the project's results through better take-up by decision makers, policy makers, industry, scientific community.

Definition of **dissemination** adopted by OpenUP⁸:

Dissemination is an activity that can be targeted at academia as well as at broader audiences. One of the crucial characteristics is that dissemination facilitates research uptake and understanding. It is a planned process that involves consideration of target audiences; consideration of the settings in which research findings are to be received; and communicating and interacting with wider audiences in ways that will facilitate research uptake in decision-making processes and practice (where appropriate).

In an **open science context**, dissemination is increasingly done at earlier stages of the research lifecycle⁹. Dissemination is becoming an integral part of the whole research workflow and more interactive. As a result, it is often difficult to draw the line between the activities of dissemination and participation.

Innovative dissemination goes beyond traditional academic publishing (e.g. academic journals, books, or monographs), conferences and workshops. An activity is only considered to be dissemination when it facilitates research uptake and understanding. For example, a citizen science project, where citizens are involved in data collection, but are not educated about the research, would not be considered as an example of innovative dissemination.

2. Results

2.1. Stakeholder analysis

In our previous work we have identified various stakeholders of research dissemination¹⁰. We categorized them according to their main role in the innovative dissemination projects that we analysed.

⁶ **Disseminating to businesses:** <https://www.openuphub.eu/disseminate/guidelines/disseminating-to-businesses>;

Disseminating to general public: <https://www.openuphub.eu/disseminate/guidelines/disseminating-to-general-public>

⁷ EC 2014, 1

⁸ Kraker et al. 2017

⁹ ibid. 9-10

¹⁰ Kraker et al. 2017, 58 ff.

In these case studies we focused on researchers and research projects as our primary stakeholders. The innovative dissemination projects as well as the tools used can be explored through the dissemination toolbox on the OpenUP Hub¹¹.

The stakeholders can take various **roles** in the dissemination process:

- Initiators: Entities which initiate the dissemination process.
- Intermediaries: Entities which support or intermediate the dissemination process.
- Target audiences: Targeted recipients of the dissemination process.
- Management: Entities which are very keen on research being disseminated and try to guide and stimulate dissemination.

Figure 1. Stakeholders of innovative dissemination, categorized according to their main role.

<p>1) Initiators</p> <p>a) Researchers</p> <p>b) Research projects</p> <p>c) Research organisations</p>	<p>2) Intermediaries</p> <p>a) Publishers</p> <p>b) Librarians</p> <p>c) Journalists</p> <p>d) Science communicators</p> <p>e) Service providers</p>	<p>3) Target audiences</p> <p>a) Researchers</p> <p>b) Teachers</p> <p>c) Students</p> <p>d) Schoolchildren</p> <p>e) Policy makers/ government</p> <p>f) Practitioners</p> <p>g) Journalists</p> <p>h) Industry/business</p> <p>i) Charities/NGOs</p> <p>j) Citizen scientists</p> <p>k) General public</p>
<p>4) Management</p> <p>a) Research organisations</p> <p>b) Funders</p>		

(Source: Kraker et al. 2017, 59)

In this deliverable we focus on **businesses and general public as target audiences**. The following paragraphs summarise results from the communication expert interviews, in particular needs and requirements by the two target groups. The results are reported in more detail in a previous deliverable¹².

2.1.1. Businesses

In general, businesses want to stay up to date about what is going on in research projects and not miss latest developments that are relevant for their own developments, services and products. This is particularly true for businesses without an own R&D department. Business audiences are not that much interested in getting to know comprehensive technical details; they want to know what the main output is, how it can help the company and how they can apply it.

Businesses are also interested in finding new R&D cooperation partners, e.g. to outsource R&D activities, share resources, or validate research done in-house. In this context having strong IPRs is very important for businesses.

In some areas, e.g. in health society or public technology, businesses need input from independent research providing independent data confirming that their products are safe, have an effect, or an

¹¹ <https://www.openuphub.eu/tools>

¹² Vignoli 2017, 19 ff.

overall positive risk-benefit balance. Examples are public debates with environmental organisations or the general public.

The need by businesses to receive information from some research areas (e.g. arts and humanities, social sciences) might not seem evident. In these areas, there is a bigger discrepancy between science and businesses.

In commissioned consulting, businesses expect the researchers to deliver a clear and quick answer to a problem. They are not looking for possible solutions and their caveats; they want clear answers that help them solving problems that they encounter in practice.

Depending on the research area, information required from research varies. For example, in the manufacturing industry information is needed to reduce costs, make products more attractive, and to maintain/achieve the pole position on market.

On the one hand, industry is interested in using the results from research. For them it is essential to know how to access the results, under which licenses, and if they are openly available. It is important for them to know which IPRs apply and which of the results can be reused. This information should be well understandable.

On the other hand, businesses do not only need research outputs such as concrete results, papers, patents. They are interested in updates on any latest research development. This can include everything up to messages or short reports on what you are up to right now.

Businesses also need people. They want to know principle investigators in their own sectors to be able to collaborate. Not only do they want to know about events that researchers are attending. They are also looking for individual experts in the field and their expertise. Businesses are always looking for opportunities to get to know researchers and find possible collaboration opportunities.

2.1.2. General Public

The general public is a very large and heterogeneous group, and without having a specific subgroup in mind it is difficult to pinpoint their interest. In many cases, the general public is not actively looking for specific information from research. However, citizens are generally interested in understanding how science is trying to solve current or upcoming challenges.

The general public is interested in a lot of science contents; it does not matter if it is cancer research, chemistry, biology etc. What is important is that they can get something away from the story, and that they gained some knowledge in this process. They are interested in science e.g. due to personal reasons, a pure interest to learn new knowledge, or because they have a particular problem that they want to solve.

Some stakeholders from the general public (e.g. patients) have a major interest to talk to the experts and to get actively involved in research - either due to their personal situation or their enthusiasm or passion for science. Be aware that if you highlight researchers in your communication strategy, individual citizens or patient organisations might contact them directly.

Everything that is being researched will find interest somewhere at the general public. However, it should be disseminated in an appropriate format. The general public is interested in information that has a direct connection to whatever is on their mind at the moment. There are moments in which citizens are interested in something specific, e.g. if they need to decide on a treatment or to deal with pollution in their garden. But when they are looking for input and evidence it is really hard for them to find. There is a disconnection between research information providers and receivers: there are a lot of flashpoints and need to understanding research information. However, when citizens are in need for this information, it is often not provided on the channels that they are looking at. If the research community becomes more open to discuss and actively participate in public debates, it would be easier for the general public to find research information.

Some citizens are also interested in finding expert contact persons. For instance, in the health research area individual citizens might contact researchers who are declared as contact persons for specific research projects or areas.

2.2. Communication guidelines and good practices

The following paragraphs summarise good practices and guidelines for communicating to businesses and the general public identified through the interviews with science communication experts¹³ and initial feedback received from the research community who tested the guidelines in context of OpenUP's fifth pilot study¹⁴.

2.2.1. Defining key messages and communication formats for reaching businesses

- Before defining key messages and communication formats it is essential to define who the specific audience is, e.g. pharma industry, telecom manufacturers, etc. The more specific the better.
- When you define your communication plan, define a timeframe and milestones for identifying the audience and start disseminating to them. Make sure to appoint persons responsible for these tasks.
- Align research communication and key messages with what the targeted businesses do. Transform the message to fit the targeted businesses' requirements and expectations.
- Explain what you are doing and get the key message to your audience. Start with the knowledge base that they already have by involving their world in the story. As a result, the message will be easier to understand, and it gets a personal touch.
- Be open to discussions, and have a platform for businesses to enable a two-way communication.
- The specifications of the requested research reports are set and communicated by the company (particularly in commissioned research settings). In these cases, the company should receive the information in exactly the format requested. Businesses will have trained staff who can deal with scientific information.
- Clarify the IPR beforehand: make sure that relevant and sensitive results are only available for the company.
- There is no format fitting all sectors and businesses. Choose formats suitable for presenting to and discussing with target audiences from the targeted sector in a two-way communication.
- It is recommendable not to go just with one format. Use 3-4 main formats that your target audience uses.
- Think multi-canal and multi-format. Do not put all energy in one big campaign. Use various tools, e.g. video, social media strategy, marketing actions, paid media, price relations, public relations (influential bloggers).
- Communication material should be in the language that your target audience understands best. To achieve a broad dissemination, in particular for EU projects, use English as dissemination language. For national projects use the national language; but always provide an executive summary in English.
- Directly involve your target groups in face-to-face events or meetings (e.g. special workshops for industry partners organised in context of research projects).
- Educate your target business by inviting them to talks and conferences where the research is being showcased.
- Advertise and disseminate these events via social media channels (e.g. Twitter, LinkedIn). ResearchGate is not recommended as this network is mostly used to reach peers from research. Please consult also the new H2020 Social Media Guide for EU funded R&I projects¹⁵.

2.2.2 Defining key messages and communication formats for reaching the general public

- Before defining key messages and communication formats it is essential to define who is your target audience. Identify a specific group that might be interested in your research, e.g. children, adults, students, senior citizens, parents.

¹³ Vignoli 2017, 23 ff.

¹⁴ <http://openup-h2020.eu/work-packages/pilot-5/>

¹⁵ European Commission 2018

- When you define your communication plan, define a timeframe and milestones for identifying the audience and start disseminating to them. Make sure to appoint persons responsible for these tasks.
- Explain research outcomes through the big picture. The communication format should not be too technical and it should tell a story. By following a storyline, complex topics can be more easily communicated to citizens. Write so that everyone can understand rather than to sound smart¹⁶.
- Attach the topic to a sensational detail to draw interest and to engage your audience. Tell a story¹⁷.
- Explain what research does to improve their life and relate it to their everyday life.
- There is communication format fitting all general public target audiences. Flexibility is the key, and the format to be chosen depends on your dissemination objectives.
- There are many possibilities, e.g. organising a big communication campaign; targeting a very specific target group (e.g. patients); or provide plain information that people are waiting for.
- It is recommendable to go with the social media trend and use, next to text, visual online resources (e.g. videos, animations). The latter are more appealing and easy to share. Using social media such as Facebook, LinkedIn, or Twitter helps gaining some visibility. Please consult also the new H2020 Social Media Guide for EU funded R&I projects¹⁸.
- It is recommendable to not only provide information, but to stimulate a dialogue with your general public target audience. This needs creativity and flexibility. Think about applying Citizen Science approaches.
- Organise or participate in events targeting general public audiences (e.g. EU researchers' nights targeting school or high-school children as well as adults).

2.2.3. Opportunities of Open Science dissemination to the general public

In his Science Communication Manifesto, Eagleman (2013) lists 6 opportunities of public dissemination of science:

1. **Thank your funders: the taxpayers.** Inform the general public about the results of research funded through public money. Provide them with the means to understand and even re-use the results.
2. **Inspire critical thinking.** Support the general public to recognise non-evidence-based approaches and expose fuzzy thinking. This helps creating a knowledge society.
3. **Stem the flow of bad information.** Media channels have a great hold on public dialog but do not always get the facts straight. Practising scientists should share more information and get involved in public dialogue. This can inspire the public to care about the value of validity.
4. **Inform public policy** to prevent public misunderstanding.
5. **Clarify what science is and is not.** The public must understand and have an appreciation of the uncertainty inherent in the scientific process.
6. **Share the raw beauty of the scientific pursuit.** Make people passionate about research, the scientific processes, results and possibilities offered through it.

2.3. Analysis of existing role descriptions, required skills, and task descriptions

In the following paragraphs we summarise the results of our analysis of existing role and job descriptions. For this study we searched the internet for job descriptions in science communication, science journalism, and public relations in research areas in currently open calls for open positions. In addition, we reviewed papers and studies about science communication particularly focusing on

¹⁶ Leeming 2016

¹⁷ McMartin 2014

¹⁸ European Commission 2018

communicating research information to target audiences outside academia. Recommendations to various stakeholder groups as well as opportunities of Open Science Dissemination are summarised as well.

Our desk research was mainly focused on existing role descriptions upon which we can build the definition of the newly emerging Open Science Communication Expert role. We did not address the question at which institutional level (e.g. research project staff; marketing and communications department; library services) this position should be allocated.

2.3.1. Tasks & required skills profile

According to Leeming (2017), people willing to work in science communication are passionate about science, understand many different, difficult topics, and are able to interact with scientists and experts. Also, they should be able to convince others that communication is important and have confidence in their own expertise, on how to communicate and with whom.

The analysed job descriptions¹⁹ target mostly early career researchers who desire to engage media and communicate with non-scientific and non-expert audiences (Duke University 2018). The following minimum requirements for applying for a position in science communication were defined by the institutions:

- Bachelor/undergraduate degree in communication, journalism, OR a science relevant to the research focus of the institute/organisation where the position is vacant.
- Ability to write and frame clear, compelling stories and issues for the press and/or multimedia content.
- Ability to quickly understand complex/sophisticated science topics and communicate them in an engaging way to a general audience.
- Experience in the strategic use of social media²⁰, web publishing and communications tools/channels.
- Excellent written, oral, interpersonal, and communication skills.
- Ability to interact effectively with researchers, administrators, and the press.

In terms of previous work experience, the analysed job descriptions required applicants to have at least 3-5 years' experience with science reporting, writing, and multimedia production, depending on their degree. Berkeley Lab (2018) and Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution (2018) require at least 5 years' experience by undergraduates, and at least 3 years' experience by graduates. Duke University (2018) preferred applicants with advanced degree in the sciences or science journalism with more than three years of media outreach or press experience.

Two job descriptions require the applicants in addition to develop and execute a media relations and communications strategy (Berkeley Lab 2018, Duke University 2018).

The following preferred qualifications were defined by the analysed job descriptions:

- Visual intelligence; photography/multimedia skills
- Experience with desktop publishing/graphic design

2.3.2. Further recommendations for actors and target groups of research dissemination

Acatech (2017) derived 12 recommendations for actors and target groups of research dissemination and communication in a digital world²¹. The following recommendations are relevant in terms of fostering good open science communication:

¹⁹ Berkeley Lab (2018), Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution (2018), Duke University (2018), University of Maryland (2018). The analysed job descriptions are included in Appendix II.

²⁰ Berkeley Lab 2018 listed experiences with social media as additional desired qualifications

²¹ Six of the recommendations translated to English by Fingerle 2017.

1. Policy makers
 - a. **Support independent science information provision**, e.g. by creating a national research communication and information platform. Science journalism has a key role here and needs more support. (Recommendation 2)
 - b. **Support science journalism activities with funding** (analogously to research funding). (Recommendation 4)
2. Researchers and research institutions
 - a. **Prevent misdirected incentives and investigate suitable indicators.** Traditional science dissemination, science journalism and dissemination through social media through researchers are complementary activities that should not be played against each other. Use of social media is particularly useful for institutions to reach out to target groups and initiate a dialogue with them. (Recommendation 5)
 - b. This includes **providing training opportunities for scientists.**
 - c. **Clearly divide fact based science communication and science marketing.** Through direct communication with end user target groups, new responsibilities arise. Institutions, academies and researchers should make sure to provide the public with reliable information. (Recommendation 7)
 - d. **Develop a quality-oriented code of behaviour (code of conduct) for science communication through the web** and, in particular, social media. (Recommendation 8)
 - e. **Increase public communication and ensure transparency of roles.** Scientists should be encouraged to position themselves publicly as experts. Their corresponding role (for example expert, teacher or private person) should be made transparent, and they should deal responsibly with time and financial resources available to them alongside their research and teaching. (Recommendation 10)
3. Universities and science policy
 - a. **Improve and massively promote skills in the evaluation of digital media and sources.**
4. Future research
 - a. **More research about the effects of digital media on scientific communication** is needed.

On a final note, we want to emphasise the role of intermediaries, which support or intermediate the dissemination process between researchers/research organisations and target audiences. Publishers, journalists or science communicators have access to media outlets and can support dissemination to general audiences as well. As an example, Frontiers for Young Minds²² help authors reach children between 8 and 15 years old.

3. Defining the role of Open Science Communication Expert: Conclusions and recommendations

In the light of the recent debate around “alternative facts” and “degraded public discourse” (Ferber 2018), immediate call to action to improve communication of research information to general public audiences becomes evident. Eagleman (2013), Libutti & Valente (2006), and already Callon (1999) made clear that communicating and interacting with the public is essential to improve perception and awareness of science. The growing need for improved and more interactive public communication of fact based science is accompanied by a substantial gap in the current science communication system. Science communication is divided between dissemination of research outcomes to peers, which is done by researchers (e.g. at conferences, in scientific publications); and popular, general public-targeted communication of research information, which is traditionally done by research journalists, communication departments or intermediaries. However, public communication of research cannot longer be carried out by professional general public and specialist media alone. Researchers need to increasingly become active and involved in public dissemination and debates instead of operating

²² <https://kids.frontiersin.org/>

behind closed academic doors. In the 21st century science and media landscape social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter and YouTube play a crucial role to reach out for public audiences (Fingerle 2017). This requires science communication experts to adapt to these new media.

Reaching out to public target audiences requires specific skills for which researchers are traditionally not trained for. As we have made clear in this document, there is an **increasing need to fill the gap between scientific, “complex” dissemination to an expert public and a more popular, “simplified” communication to public target audiences**. Targeted and interactive Open Science Communication should be supported on policy and institutional level to increase active participation by researchers. In this context, additional **funding** of science communication activities, setting appropriate **incentives** and providing communication and soft-skills **training** for researchers are key factors.

To fill this gap, we propose to **create new science communication roles and positions** to be staffed with people both **skilled in science communication and with science expert knowledge**. Currently, researchers and science journalists do not necessarily have the necessary skills, and they can definitely not cover the additional effort coming with Open Science Communication activities on top of their current tasks. It is important to have, next to PR and marketing staff, trained experts with the necessary scientific background and skills, who are also trained in communicating to and interacting with audiences outside the research community by means of Web 2.0 technologies. Policy makers and strategic HR should see this as a chance to create new jobs for the growing number of qualified young researchers, who currently only have poor access to the job market in research and academia.

4. Literature

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Appendix I

Table with overview of draft recommendations and guidelines for communicating research to businesses and the general public. The draft guidelines have been tested and reviewed by the research project ReFlex²³ in context of OpenUP's fifth pilot study. The guidelines are currently being revised and expanded based on the comments received. The final version will be made available on the OpenUP Hub²⁴.

Table 2. Draft recommendations for reaching businesses and the public: Overview table (Version 2)

Steps	Guiding questions	Expert Tips	
		Communicating to businesses	Communicating to general public
1. Define dissemination & communication objectives	What do you want to achieve by targeting the specific audience? Think about your goals.	Involve business partner in a research project and/or collaboration. Get the business perspective to gain new insights for further research. Have a prototype developed in a real-life context. Commercialize your results.	Think about your goals: e.g. do you want feedback, to spark debate, to influence behaviours, to invite collaboration, to influence decision-makers?
	What is the purpose of the communication to the specific target group? Think about what your audience should be able to do with your information.	Achieve/ maintain the pole position in market based on scientific validated results. Drive innovation in both products and services. Increase quality of the products and services using new technologies. Make products that are safety, appealing and competitive (cost reduction). Validate research done in-house. Find R&D collaboration.	How do you want the information to be used? Do you want to engage research participants (via Citizen Science)?
2. Define target audience(s)	Who is your main target audience? Think about who exactly you are trying to reach. Break down and define your target group(s).	- Large and medium companies with R&D lab - SMEs (without lab) - Startups - Business sector-company association - Creative industry - NGOs - CSOs	The general public is a very large group, and without having a specific sub-group in mind it is difficult to pinpoint their interest. Build a picture of your audiences, their motivations and experiences. Understanding will help you engage.

²³ <http://reflex-smartgrid.eu/>

²⁴ <https://www.openuphub.eu/disseminate/guidelines>

	<p>Get to know your target audience, their needs and expectations of the research outcomes, as well as their preferred communication channels</p>	<p>Keep business informed on what is going on research project/ updates on latest research developments. Clarify the IPR beforehand: make sure that relevant and sensitive results are only available for the company.</p>	<p>Can you organise survey or focus groups with your target audience to better understand them?</p>
<p>3. Define key message(s)</p>	<p>Make sure that the key messages and information that you provide is relevant for the targeted audience. Align your key message with what the targeted audiences expect.</p>	<p>Think about “What can a particular business get out of your research”. Select just one or two key aspects that are the easiest to showcase and grasp.</p>	<p>“How does science solve problems that our society faces?” Also: people are curious and want to learn something new.</p>
	<p>Explicitly include and address the targeted audience in the key message. Start with the knowledge base that they already have by involving their world in the story.</p>	<p>Identify the specific needs of the targeted business and design your key messages by addressing how your research can be beneficial to the specifics of their field.</p>	<p>Relate to the everyday lives of your target audience.</p>
<p>4. Plan your dissemination & communication strategy</p>	<p>Define dissemination channels and media format. Choosing media, format and dissemination strategy strongly depends on your communication objectives.</p>	<p>Use 2-3 different media channels to transmit your message. Consider what the easiest and shortest ways would be for the business to understand your message.</p>	<p>Participate in public debates; go with the trend - social media, visual online resources (especially animations!).</p>
	<p>Structure & prepare your dissemination material. You can share your key message to reach your target audience as passive listeners.</p>	<p>Channels such as social media, information sheets and leaflets or advertisements could be useful in this case.</p>	<p>Explain through the big picture; use “sensational details” to catch attention. Tell a story that is not too technical!</p>
	<p>Follow up with your stakeholders. You can activate your target audiences and enable them to become active or do</p>	<p>Face-to-face events, meetings at your venue and networking events could be used in these cases.</p>	<p>Name contact persons; participate in interactive, public events. Laymen can give valuable insights!</p>

<p>something with the content that you provide.</p>		
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Appendix II

1. Analysed job descriptions

1.1. Science Communications & Media Relations Specialist²⁵

You will:

- Working with department colleagues and Lab experts, identify, research, write, edit, package, and assist in the distribution of informative, compelling content for a range of audiences.
- Write news releases, feature articles, and other content, often about complex scientific or institutional topics, in clear, compelling, storytelling prose.
- Stay informed of key achievements in selected scientific areas of the Lab and work with experts in those areas to develop communications strategies.
- Serve as a primary Lab point of contact for members of the news media, and work to achieve and increase coverage of the Lab's scientific work.
- Develop content focused on building engagement and awareness among Lab staff of key research and operational initiatives.
- Support and/or lead communication projects as needed.
- Back up other members of the department as needed by performing digital communications, web production, social media, news media relations, and other duties.
- Serve as a representative and ambassador for the Strategic Communications Department.
- Assume responsibility for your continuing professional growth through participation in professional meetings, membership in professional organizations, enrollment in advanced courses, and professional journals and other publications.

What is required:

- Bachelor's degree in English, journalism, communications, or a science relevant to Berkeley Lab's research, especially biosciences or equivalent experience
- At least five (5) years of related experience in organizational communications and/or journalism
- Experience and proficiency writing and editing smart, original articles about scientific research for a popular audience.
- Strong journalism-based research, interview, writing, and editing skills.
- Ability to work independently and within teams to achieve desired outcomes.
- Tech savvy and experience in the use of internal and external communications tools and channels (such as social media, WordPress, DropBox, Google Drive, etc.).
- Effective at time- and project-management skills with the ability to prioritize work assignments, work collaboratively with others, and adjust schedules based on changing requirements.

²⁵ Berkeley Lab (2018)

- Track record of working well under pressure, during tight deadlines, with humor, tact, and professionalism.
- Proven excellence in all areas of customer service.

Additional desired qualifications:

- Eight years or more of experience in organizational communications and/or journalism
- Visual intelligence and the ability to recognize and design effective visual and multimedia communication aids.
- Experience with social media in an institutional setting.
- Existing relationships with the news media and a track record of serving as a resource to reporters.
- Experience within a national laboratory or other science-based organization.

1.2. Science Writer & Multimedia Producer²⁶

REQUIRED EDUCATION & EXPERIENCE:

- Undergraduate degree in journalism, communications, science, or related field with at least 5 years' experience in science reporting, writing, multimedia production, and/or public relations; or relevant Master's degree with at least 3 years' experience in science reporting, writing, and multimedia production required.
- Proven ability to conceive and produce science articles and multimedia content. Demonstrated science journalism skills, including identifying stories, interviewing, and reporting, and the ability to quickly understand complex science topics and communicate them in an engaging way to a general audience. Flexibility to adapt to and manage sometimes rapidly shifting priorities. Experience working with scientific and technical staff to produce materials that meet with their approval, while at the same time meeting institutional and departmental goals and objectives. Applicants must provide samples of their work.
- Strong interpersonal, communication, and organizational skills essential, along with demonstrated teamwork and personal initiative. Excellent written and verbal communication skills, and strong attention to detail. Ability to work effectively in a collegial manner across all levels of the Institution, maintaining a professional demeanor. Adept at giving and receiving constructive criticism. Ability to effectively manage deadlines and multiple priorities. Demonstrated ability to use independent judgment, show initiative, and problem-solve. Literacy across a spectrum of scientific disciplines. Strong work ethic and willingness to work flexible hours to meet deadlines. TWIC required.

1.3. Science Communications Specialist²⁷

[...] this role will drive public understanding of neuroscience and promote the extraordinary people and research [...]. This is an exciting opportunity for a gifted science writer/reporter with media relations experience.

We are searching for a science writer with a demonstrated ability and desire to engage media and communicate with non-scientific and non-expert audiences. [...]

Responsibilities include, but are not limited to the following:

²⁶ Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution (2018)

²⁷ Duke University (2018)

1. Investigates, conceptualizes, and develops compelling print, web, and newsletter content to explore and explain the work of Zuckerman Institute scientists.
2. Crafts and executes a media relations and communications strategy to amplify the work of the Institute.
3. Cultivates and maintains relationships with reporters in print, digital and broadcast media.
4. Drafts and edits news releases, press materials, op-eds, and letters-to-the editor.
5. Pitches stories to the media and proactively identifies publicity opportunities to promote Zuckerman Institute research and education programs.
6. Manages and updates website.
7. Maintains a media database and performs other related duties and special projects as assigned.

Minimum Qualifications for Grade

Applicant MUST meet these minimum qualifications to be considered an applicant

Bachelor's degree and a minimum of four years of related experience is required.

Additional Position-Specific Minimum Qualifications

Applicant MUST meet these minimum qualifications to be considered an applicant

Exceptional attention to editorial detail. Must possess the ability to frame stories and issues for the press and a sophisticated understanding of science as it relates to contemporary issues and debates.

Excellent interpersonal and communications skills, a sense of humor, and a commitment to teamwork. Must be flexible, organized, and capable of performing multiple tasks.

The successful candidate must be flexible in nature, have a sound judgment with a collaborative style that fosters teamwork and cooperation beyond the immediate team to the broader organization. Must have a passion for excellent customer service and commitment to exceptional quality.

[...]

Preferred Qualifications

Advanced degree in the sciences or science journalism preferred; More than three years of media outreach or press experience preferred.

Experience with Drupal or related content management systems is highly desired; experience using Google analytics to track viewership and as a basis to inform digital strategy is preferred.

1.4. Science Communications Coordinator²⁸

[...] The primary focus of the Science Communications Coordinator is to enhance awareness and understanding of SESYNC research and opportunities within the community of socio-environmental scientists, scientific knowledge users, and policy makers. The Science Communications Coordinator will have lead responsibility for developing and coordinating communications across SESYNC's research network and with the educated public. S/he will:

- Collaborate in development and implementation of a high-impact SESYNC communications strategy;

²⁸ University of Maryland (2018)

- Develop and maintain close familiarity with SESYNC-supported research projects and key stakeholders;
- Serve as point of contact between SESYNC-supported researchers and the media;
- Coordinate communications efforts and foster collaboration with and among research teams, their home institutions, and with the broader research and education community;
- Promote the mission and research accomplishments of the SESYNC network;
- Cultivate and coordinate media outreach and placement of SESYNC results and opportunities;
- Collaborate with SESYNC staff and postdocs to develop communications and promotional materials;
- Ensure consistency of language and presentation in SESYNC's outreach and communications materials;
- Evaluate the success and efficacy of communication materials and strategies;
- Support outreach and education events and general programs including organizing and running the weekly seminar series.

Minimum Qualifications:

Bachelor's degree.

At least three years of experience in science communications to include science writing for the educated public, strategic use of social media, and content management or other forms of web publishing.

Creative self-starter with a passion for and experience in science writing.

Possess excellent written, oral, and interpersonal communication skills; ability to manage multiple projects; the ability to interact effectively with researchers, administrators, and the press; and, a demonstrated record of completing assignments.

Preferences:

Strong interest and understanding of environmental science; demonstrated ability to interact with university administrators and faculty; photography/multimedia skills; experience with desktop publishing/graphic design are preferred.